

Student Engagement in a Large Flipped Class

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Abstract

This paper reports on two criminal law classes in which I instituted a flipped-class methodology. The classes were mandatory and contained large numbers of students (over 120 in each). The asynchronous out-of-class materials were well received but students were reluctant to engage in discussions and other interactive activities in the synchronous classes. The students were much more willing to speak privately at the end of the classes, which limited their opportunities to learn from each other. Nevertheless, of the 44 students who mentioned the synchronous classes in feedback, twice as many (n=29) supported discursive and interactive classes as opposed them (n=15). The paper reviews the literature on a number of possible solutions, and concludes with some reflections on how I might adapt this literature to improve synchronous sessions as part of an overall flipped methodology.

Keywords: *Student engagement; Flipped class; Class discussion; Large classes*

1. Introduction

This paper reports on my attempts to increase student engagement through discussion and argument in two flipped Criminal Law modules, both of which contain large numbers of students. In one respect, the paper is a report on relative failure – while students appeared to be generally happy with the flipped method, as an educator I was disappointed with how the in-person sessions developed. I reflect on what went wrong, and how I might improve these results in the future.

2. Description of the Teaching/Learning Context

I have taught criminal law to undergraduate students for many years on both Law (second years) and Arts (final years) programmes. Roughly 145 and 120 students, respectively, registered for the classes, both of which were held in traditional tiered lecture halls with fixed seating and relatively good acoustics. Criminal law is a mandatory module for both sets of students. I have adopted a fully flipped methodology in both classes. A flipped class has been defined as

[A] pedagogical approach in which direct instruction moves from the group learning space to the individual learning space, and the resulting group space is transformed into a dynamic, interactive learning environment where the educator guides students as they apply concepts and engage creatively in the subject matter' (Schaffzin, 2016, p. 665-6).

I adopted this pedagogical method in the expectation that students would find greater flexibility and a deeper learning experience through this pedagogy.

I broke each topic into smaller chunks, and for each chunk I prepared narrated videos and quizzes to be viewed asynchronously. However, the founders of the flipped methodology (Bergman & Sams, 2012 and 2014) suggest that its real payoff lies in the 'use of class time for hands on activities or other means of encouraging students to practice, apply and demonstrate mastery of the content learned from the pre-class requirements' (Harris et al., 2016, p. 325). I have considerable experience with discussion-based classes at postgraduate level, although these classes typically had twelve or fewer students who were older than my undergraduate students. The postgraduate students were highly engaged, but it was unclear whether this was due to class size or to the students' relative maturity. My guess at this juncture is that the former is more likely as the postgraduates were only a year or two older than the undergraduates. I will return to the issue of class size later.

Students in both undergraduate modules were scheduled for two one-hour classes each week, one of which I used for revision and questions/answers. I designed the second session to be discursive to help students delve deeper into the material. I stressed to the students from the very first class that participation was important, and that I expected and wanted them to

engage with me and with each other. I explained that they could learn much from each other: Arvanitakis points out that ‘students in the lecture hall are not empty vessels but are themselves full of knowledge’ (2014, p. 740), and that this knowledge is a learning resource (ibid, p. 744). Further, engaging in debate is a skill that all lawyers must develop. I used *Vevox* polls, an online polling app which has been shown to increase student engagement ‘without the fear of being put on the spot to answer a question’ (Czekanski & Wolf, 2013; Greenwood, 2023; Lowney, 2023).

In a standardised feedback survey, with 149 responses between the two classes,¹ some students (n=15) indicated that they disliked these sessions, but twice as many (n=29) liked them. One said, *‘I really enjoy the class discussions which further increase learning by letting us speak and teach each other’*. Another said, *‘The in-person classes are a great overview of the topics and I really enjoy how there are times [sic] for questions when needed.’* Yet in class, most students would not volunteer to engage in discussion. But when called upon individually, they had no difficulty in answering and giving coherent opinions. As the weeks went by and it became clear that students were reluctant to speak in class, I tried asking students to raise their hands to indicate who had voted what way in the *Vevox* polls, and then called on individual students to justify their position. Perhaps predictably, the students soon learned not to raise their hands!

Fritschner (2000) sets out six levels of student participation:

- Breathing and staying awake;
- Coming to class, taking notes and completing assignments;
- Writing reflective and thoughtful papers;
- Asking questions in class, making comments and providing input for class discussions;
- Doing additional kinds of research or coming to class with additional questions; and,
- Making oral presentations where the students themselves became the teachers.

My hope coming into the semester was that students would reach at least level 4, which would indicate active learning and perhaps even critical thinking. In practice, the vast majority of students rarely exceeded level 2. Students asking their questions after class instead of during the class denied other students the opportunity to learn from those questions and the discussion that developed from them. Added to this, as noted, was students’ reluctance to volunteer answers/opinions despite being able to do so when called upon. These experiences suggest that students had not grasped how much information and understanding they can gain from each other (Precourt & Gainor, 2019; Nadile et al., 2021). As a result, students could not have derived as much from these sessions as I had hoped.

¹ With a total of 265 registered students in the two classes, the response rate was 56 percent.

3. Literature Review

The annual Irish Survey of Student Engagement confirms that a minority of students at the University of Galway take responsibility for most classroom questions and comments (ISSE, 2022).² Almost 60 percent of student respondents reported either never contributing or doing so only sometimes. This result implies that some 40 percent contribute frequently, a figure that almost certainly overstates the true level of student participation; studies have found that students seriously overestimate their own participation levels (see, e.g., Howard et al., 2002; Burchfield & Sappington, 1999). This is especially true when the estimation occurs at the end of the semester (i.e., in a student feedback survey) rather than immediately after each class (Krohn et al., 2011).

My experience has been replicated many times in the literature. Rocca notes that instructors face a ‘regular struggle to get students to ask questions and participate in discussions’ (2010, p. 185). Multiple studies have shown that a minority of students are responsible for the majority of class contributions, a situation that Karp & Yoels described as a ‘consolidation of responsibility’ (1976). In Karp & Yoels’ study, between three and five students accounted for half to three-quarters of all students’ comments in class. More recently, Howard & Henney (1998) found that 92 percent of interactions were made by around 5 ‘talkers’ (defined as students who made at least two contributions in the session; they made up less than 30 percent of the total number of students). Over half the students in the sessions in question made no contribution at all. And Howard et al. (1996) found that 28 percent of students accounted for 89 percent of all student comments.

The challenge is to find a way to encourage students to participate in large discursive classes. This is especially true now that large classes that have become such a feature of modern university education as a result of massification (Hornsby & Osman, 2014, p. 712). Cold calling is an option. Cold-calling arises when instructors call on a student individually to answer questions without waiting for that student to volunteer an answer. Not surprisingly, cold-calling results in greater and wider student participation than reliance upon voluntary responses (Carstens et al., 2016). Many academics dislike this option, believing that it makes students feel uncomfortable (Dallimore et al., 2005 and 2006). Dallimore et al. found, however, that this belief has little substance. Their study of an undergraduate management accountancy module with over 600 registered students concluded that cold-calling is ‘effective at increasing the number of students who answer questions voluntarily; furthermore, in classes with high cold-calling, voluntary participation increases over time’

² As its name suggests, the ISSE is an annual survey of third-level students about their experiences in Irish higher education institutions. Over 300,000 students have completed these surveys since 2013.

(2012, p. 306). The authors suggest that ‘cold-calling encourages students to prepare more and to participate more frequently; the more they prepare, and the more frequently they participate, the more comfortable they become when participating’ (ibid, p. 331).

Making better and more extensive use of technology that anonymises student contributions is a further option. Fassinger noted that ‘students’ reactions to a class may have more to do with peers’ behaviours than with the course structure or a faculty member’s actions’ (1996, p. 29). Similarly, Nadile et al. (2021) found that fear of being negatively evaluated on foot of questions/opinions acts as a disincentive to participation, especially among female students.³ Polling apps like *Vevox* and *Kahoot* allow students to participate anonymously as individuals (Greenwood, 2023). Other technologies such as *Padlet* allow groups to participate while retaining an element of anonymity for the individuals in those groups.

Another option is to offer some degree or level of credit for participation. Sommer & Sommer (2007) reported on an experiment in which a small amount of class credit was offered on alternate days. Participation increased on both days but the increase was significantly higher on the credit days. Similarly, Foster et al. (2009) found that low-responding students engaged more during classes in which participation credit was offered than in classes in which no credit was offered. Nevertheless, a number of practical objections can be raised to the practice. First, what credit is to be given? In the reported studies, the amount of credit on offer was low; one of the instructors in Karp & Yoels’ study (1976), for example, offered a maximum of 22.5 participation points out of a total of 520 points – less than five percent of the total score for that module. But should the credit be given to reflect the fact of the contribution or its quality? If the latter, how is the quality to be measured? And what about the process of external assessment? A further difficulty is that if participation credit is to be offered, it must be available to every student. In a small class, this is not much of a problem, but both of my criminal law classes have well over 100 registered students. Even if every minute of a session were to be given over to discussion, only a fraction of students in such a large class will be able to participate. The likelihood of complaints and appeals is obvious. Finally, on a purely logistical level, recording participation scores will add to the instructor’s burden in every class. Krohn et al. (2011), however, suggest allowing students to self-record their participation, and found a high degree of agreement between such self-reports and independent observation where the self-reporting was done at the end of each class.

Finally, we might attempt to deal with the underlying issue: the existence of large classes. Rocca (2010) notes a considerable body of research demonstrating that students are more likely to participate in a smaller class than in a larger class. One of the earliest studies, done by Karp & Yoels (1976), found that both students and teachers considered large class sizes to be an impediment to students engaging in class discussions. Their study confirmed these

³ I have not considered the gender and age make-up of classes as these are issues over which a teacher has little control, especially in mandatory modules.

sentiments: students in smaller classes were twice as likely to participate as students in larger classes (48 percent as opposed to 24 percent), and were five times more likely to make two or more contributions. Fassinger (1996) found that students making more than one contribution was the norm in smaller classes (twenty or fewer students) but not in larger classes (52 percent versus 29 percent). Similarly, Fritschner (2000) found that almost half of all interactions (47 percent) occurred in smaller upper classes, against only 29 percent in the larger introductory classes. Indeed, Howard and Henney (1996) concluded that ‘the effect of larger class size [is] the largest significant predictor of student participation’. These studies suggest that breaking a large class into several smaller groups might be the easiest way to encourage greater student participation in class discussions (Ferguson, 1986, p. 217-8). There is a limit, however, on what individual academics can do. Large classes are a reality, and the resources made available to universities have not kept pace with the massification of third-level education and are unlikely to do so in the future (Hornsby & Osman, 2014, p. 713).

4. Reflection

In many respects, flipping my criminal law modules was a success but the in-person discursive sessions were disappointing due to the unwillingness of students to engage in discussion and debate. These are large classes (well over 100 students in each), and as noted, the literature shows that student engagement tends to be greater in smaller groups. Individual lecturers in mandatory modules have little control over the number of students registering in their classes. It is not open to me to simply cut the number of students in my criminal law classes, no matter how well advised doing so might be pedagogically. But there are other steps that might be taken to align classes with the literature, especially in the context of a flipped methodology. Rather than all students being required to attend all in-person sessions every week, perhaps I might divide the cohort into four sub-groups, with each attending on successive weeks. As the students will already have had the benefit of the pre-recorded classes, a reduction in scheduled class times should be officially permissible. But it might be argued that reducing class time undermines one of the principal benefits of flipping classes – providing time for students to engage in activities that will help to develop their mastery of the subject. Perhaps in an ideal world. But in a world of large classes that militates against student participation, it is surely better to have fewer in-person classes that are of a higher participatory quality.

Reducing class sizes is only one aspect of improving student engagement; other logistical issues intersect with class size to affect such engagement. The architecture of the classroom is one such issue (O’Hare, 1998; Kennedy (2002). Traditional lecture halls and classrooms are not particularly helpful for hands-on group activities (Wannarka & Ruhl, 2008). Rocca (2010) points to literature that found that classrooms in which seats/desks can be arranged in a circular or a U-shape encourage greater levels of student participation. Thus, it might be better to use classes designed for problem-based learning. In Galway, we have a new moot

court room that is especially advantageous – it is relatively small with movable furniture and is well served technologically (two large screens). These factors will allow me to divide the class into even smaller groups of three or four to work on problems together as well as individually. Teachers should also get over their aversion to cold-calling, which does not have to be a confrontational, adversarial process. In a more intimate setting than a traditional lecture, in which the learning materials and outcomes have been identified to students in advance, cold calling can be done in a relaxed and informal way.

Discussion and argument are valuable skills for law students to develop, and the use of polling apps like *Vevox* are excellent tools to kickstart discussions. But the scaled-down flipped in-person class set out above is an excellent opportunity to introduce more realistic problem-solving skills. In my classes, I drew up specially prepared and accurate Books of Evidence that contained indictments, charge sheets and witness statements that were presented more realistically than the traditional one-paragraph scenario. Groups of three or four students can work on these Books of Evidence together, presenting their conclusions to the whole group via *Padlet* or some such technology. Apps such as these allow students a degree of anonymity in that the results presented to the class will be done as a group, thereby ticking yet another participation box.

Finally, some academic credit *could* be offered for attendance and participation, and as noted, there is some research to suggest that participation rates increase by doing so. I confess, however, that I rebel against the idea of giving academic credit to law students for merely doing the most basic of Fritschner's (2000) levels of participation, which they should be doing anyway. From this strategy, therefore, I respectfully dissent.

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